

Yorùbá Traditional Religion

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Yorùbá Traditional Religion The Yorùbá are a distinct ethnic group found across a few countries of west Africa. They òconsider Ilé-Ife as their ancestral home from where they migrated to all locations where they are currently found. They occupy the entire southwest Nigeria and are found in groups in Nigeria's north central states of Kwara and Kogi as well as in the South-south region of Edo and Delta. The Yorùbá people are also found in places like Ghana, Benin Republic and Togo. The people have a rich cultural heritage which includes their religion. Scholars, while dissecting their religious practises have suggested several terminologies to describe their religious eco-system. Their indigenous religious structure has been described as polytheism, Poly-monotheism and diffused monotheism to mention a few. Their indigenous religious architecture has attracted such robust appraisal and reappraisal owing to its uniqueness, colour, glamour and the ingenuity of the people regarding their faith life. The Yorùbá have Olódúmarè at the apex of their religion. He is assisted in administering the universe by his retinue of deities (òrisà). The òrisà are of two classes. The first are the primordial deities and the second, deified gods/ancestors. Primordial deities among the Yorùbá include Ọbàtálá or Ọrúnmilà, Èsù while deified gods include Sàngó and Oya. Below the òrisà are the personification of natural forces. The spirits/ghosts/apparitions and other phenomena are classified next to the natural forces. There is another class of beings (previously humans) who are looked upon as having attained some degree of awe, worship and reference. They are the ancestors who lived a good life and have transited the earthly realm to the realm beyond. Olódúmarè is conceived as the almighty, the controller of the universe and the force behind order and symphony in the world. He is however held as being too busy with other issues beyond the daily running of the universe and has therefore placed the administration of the earth in the care of the numerous òrisà who have their areas of specialization while intervening in human affairs. They òrisà are consulted by humans whenever they seek solutions to issues that confront them. Some of the òrisà are reputed as fertility gods/goddesses, others are consulted for vengeance on enemies, while some still are reputed for their strength in wars, battles and difficult challenges. Both the primordial deities and deified gods attend to the numerous challenges brought to them by members of the human community. The difference between the two classes of deities has become very blur such that many times, the deified gods are sometimes spoken of and treated as primordial deities. In the past, the Yorùbá depended on natural forces for protection. They relied on hills, mountains, rivers and forests/caves as defence against enemies. Many Yorùbá villages and communities soon began to venerate such natural forces either as fertility gods/goddesses or as their protectors. Olósúnta rock (Ikere Ekiti), Ọṣun river (Osogbo) Oke Ibadan (Ibadan) are good examples of personification of natural forces in Yorubaland. Some of the deities are also reputed to deploy natural forces like thunder, whirlwind, and storms (eg. Sàngó) in the defence of their votaries. Besides the natural forces, the Yorùbá also belief in Spirits, apparitions and ghosts. They recognise spirits that inhabit forests, trees and other natural elements. Ancestors are the closest of the non-human/divine beings which the Yorùbá people recognise. They are believed to be around and always present within the human community they once lived in. They are moral agents who listen to every conversation, pay attention to the strict observance of taboos and every other aspect of the lives of the people. They could reward and punish for good and bad conducts. Aside those in their ancestral homes, Africans in the diaspora also exported their religions in their sojourns and have continued to identify with their deities and other traditional practices for several centuries. For examples, in places like Trinidad and Tobago, Brazil, Cuba, Portugal among others, Africans and in this case, the Yorùbá have continued to showcase their religion and culture in territories and nations where they are found. The Yorùbá indigenous religion is indeed complex but exciting. Unlike some world religions, they are not prone

to religious extremism which breeds violence and intolerance. Rather, each religious group observes their festivals, ceremonies and worship without the fear of violence from other groups. Religious syncretism is at its peak among the people. Votaries of one religious group accompany their friends and relations to worship their deities and they reciprocate this gesture to one another during their religious observances. The religious festivals of the people are usually colourful, lively and full of symbols. They begin their traditional year, planting seasons, harvest times and indeed all their significant occasions with prayers and veneration to their gods and goddesses who are believed to be intermediaries between Olódúmarè and human beings. The gods/goddesses know their boundaries and do not ascribe to themselves the honour that is due to the supreme being. Rather, they are said to receive the sacrifice from the human community and present them to Olódúmarè for His attention and approval.

Date Range: 1100 CE - 2024 CE

Region: West Africa, Nigeria, Togo and Benin Republic

Region tags: Africa

South west Nigeria, parts of north central and south south Nigeria and some areas in Benin Republic and northern Togo

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bolaji, Idowu. OLODUMARE: God in Yoruba Belief. London: Longmans, 1966.
- Source 2: Ologundudu, Dayo. The Cradle of Yoruba Culture. USA: Center for Spoken Words/ Institute of Yoruba Culture, 2008.
- Source 3: Awolalu, Omosade. Yoruba Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites. Hallow, Essex, UK: Longman, 1981.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/219809>
- Source 1 Description: Falola, Toyin, and Jacob K. Olupona. "African Traditional Religions in Contemporary Society" 24, no 2 (1991)
- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3601642>
- Source 1 Description: O'Hear, Ann, Jacob K. Olupona, and Toyin Falola. "Religion and Society in Nigeria: Historical and Sociological Perspectives." no 20 (1992)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.20431/2347-3134.0510003>
- Source 1 Description: "Dramatic Aspect of Ese Ifa in Yorubaland" 5. no.10 (2017)
- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3334875>.
- Source 1 Description: Drewal, Henry, Judith Gleason, Awotunde Aworinde, and John Olaniyi Ogundipe. "A

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Yorùbá traditional religious group, as the name implies originates from the Yorùbá people. It is practiced by people who are primarily indigenous to the tribe. The peoples' traditional homeland includes southwest Nigeria and parts of the south-south (Itsekiri, Delta State) and north central region (Kwara and Kogi State) of the country. They are also found in parts of Benin Republic and Togo. Aside their fair populations in other regions of the world where they have exported their religious values as a well-travelled group, the era of the slave trade saw their forced mass exodus to the Americas and other foreign lands where they have continued to practice their religion for centuries. So, the people are in cultural contact with other religious groups. They have been quite accommodating of other religious ideologies and practices.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the cultural contact in the target region is competitive.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is accommodating/pluralistic

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group is neutral in their interactions with other religious groups. However, this form of relationship has not been reciprocated by other religious groups which have emerged in the traditional homeland of the Yorùbá people. There have been instances where adherents of the religious group have been discriminated against and maligned by other religious groups.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Although there have not been cases of physical violence between religious groups in Yorùbáland recently there have been resistance in thoughts and principles between adherents of different religious groups due to government educational policies (especially in Osun and Kwara States) suspected to be favourable to some groups at the expense of others.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: There have not been reports of the group being targeted for violent attacks outside the sample region although other religious groups have suffered some form of violent attacks especially in Northern Nigeria. It may be argued that they have not been targeted due to their very negligible numbers in these places.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The group has no strict general process, system or conditions to be fulfilled by would-be members before membership status is accorded them. Membership is usually obtained through two major avenues. It is mostly drawn through birth into the families of existing members or by those who have obtained the benevolence of the gods and are willing to join the group as a mark of gratitude to the gods that have saved them from some form of life crisis.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not actively proselytize or recruit new members. Their membership increases or decreases in direct response to the benevolence or otherwise of the gods to the human population within their region of operation. A form of religious revival or re-awakening could be heralded when the gods intervene either in the personal life (in the case of individuals), family life (in the case of a nuclear or extended family) or communal life (of a whole village, town etc). The intervention or otherwise often determines membership subscription and commitment to the gods or their staying at abeyance from them.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Politicians do not often openly identify with the Yorùbá Traditional Religious groups although there are claims that they secretly patronise them for political gains including election victories, all manners of traditional magic and charms for protection of lives etc

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Since the Yorùbá Traditional Religious system has being termed as diffused monotheism or mono-polytheism, individuals are free to participate in the religious festivals of any, many or several of the distinct religious groups that make up the Yorùbá Traditional Religious system. To this extent, apostasy is not an issue with the Yorùbá Traditional Religious system. Even when some folks change their religious affiliation to other faiths outside the Yorùbá autochthonous religious groups, they are not often tagged apostates as the case is when such movement is from the Abrahamic faiths to the traditional religious groups.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000000

Notes: Although there is an ongoing resurgence in membership of the different faith groups which make up the Yorùbá Traditional Religious system, it is still safe to retain a conservative number of the adherents of these collection of faith groups which make up the indigenous religious system of the Yorùbá people.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Each group has its recognised leaders among the faith communities which make up the Yorùbá indigenous religious system.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: In each religious group, the titles held by each functionary/religious specialist of the group determines their duties/roles and consequently, their hierarchy within the groups. Among the gods or deities, this idea of hierarchy also exists. For example, Ọ̀bàtálá (Ọ̀bàtáàsà) in some spheres referred to as Ọ̀rúnmílà is reputed to be next in rank to Olódúmarè (the supreme being). He was consequently assigned the most crucial assignment during the creation, vis; the moulding of the physical frame of the first humans before Olódúmarè, using his superior might breathed into their nostrils to give life to humans.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

Notes: Although there is usually the highest ranking member of each traditional religious group among the Yorùbá, such highly ranked member isn't usually the only/single leader of a local community/religious group.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Although each Yorùbá indigenous religious group has their leaders, there is usually no hierarchy among them when the groups come together. In some cases, age constitutes a subtle defining factor for respect and authority. However, expertise and thorough training also confers on younger religious specialists some degree of respect and standing among the aged in the leadership hierarchy of the indigenous religious

groups among the Yorùbá. This is not to say that there are no specialists in certain areas of need among them. Specialists of each religious group is simply consulted for what they know how to do best while the groups subsequently forge ahead after this.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: This is not cast in stone. For the reason of coordination, there may sometimes be the need for 'regional' leaders who - for want of a better word - oversee other leaders. However, the general practice is that each local group is autonomous of the other and operates independently of others though they seek collaboration among each other.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The real function of regional leaders is not that of overseeing but exerting some subtle influence within their area of influence while allowing local leaders perform their duties.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The groups are not particular about the strata/layers or leadership hierarchy in their groups. They seem to place premium on group cohesion above any other consideration although some allude to having fully experienced specialists and trainee specialists distinct from members or followers of the groups.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: Leaders are only believed to reflect or showcase some aspects of the powers inherent in the gods. They are believed to be able to demonstrate these powers as much as they are given access by the gods. Their capacity to do this depends on their dedication to the gods, their mastery of the art and acts of manipulating the process of divination, contemplation and their skilfulness in manoeuvring processes of offering sacrifices to them etc.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Religious leaders among adherents of the Yorùbá indigenous religious traditions are chosen in some cases. In other cases, signs exist among them (as they claim) to determine leaders and successors to leadership positions.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: This happens in some cases. However, Ifá (the oracle) chooses leaders in other cases.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: This also happens in some cases. Kings and traditional title holders in traditional religious groups in Yorùbáland have roles to perform in the emergence of leaders in some instances. For example, the Ooni of Ife (the Traditional ruler of the ancient historical city of Ile-Ife) announces the installation of some high calibre Ifa functionaries in Ile-Ife, the religious capital of Yorùbáland.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

Notes: Followers are at liberty to make charges of fallibility against their leaders. However, this does not usually happen.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Other leaders in the religious group could make charges of fallibility against their leader but this does not usually happen.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: This does not usually happen in relation to matters of their faith. However, leaders of a traditional religious group could be charged and pronounced innocent or guilty of an offence in civil or criminal matters before a court of competent jurisdiction

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Their scriptures are largely oral and have been passed down several generations. Attempts are currently being intensified to document some of these oral scriptures for the benefit of humanity.

↳ Are they written:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: There are several stories behind the revelation of scriptures used by the traditional religious groups among the Yorùbá

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the scriptures are said to have been received by the inspiration of the high god.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Some of their scriptures are revealed by the interventions of other deities among the Yorùbá people.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the scriptures of the indigenous religious groups to Yorùbáland also originate from divine or semi-divine human beings. They recount experiences of some spirit beings and ancestors and their victories which spur the living members of their group to similar feat while singing or chanting scriptures believed to be potent over challenging situations.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: There are several stories behind the revelations of most of the oral scriptures used among the traditional religious groups among the Yorùbá

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: Although the scriptures are not alterable, they could be manipulated to serve counter positions of contending parties. Other stronger or more potent scriptures could be deployed by opposing forces to counter the claims made with respect to other scriptures employed or consulted by other parties to disputes or spiritual contentions.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 5

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 30

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 30

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 10

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 5

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Statues, evil forests, spiritually energised/charged buildings etc

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Visits to Ile-Ife used to be considered as pilgrimages in the past. This is not a usual practice in recent times.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: A spirit-body distinction is present among the various religious groups that make up the Yorùbá Traditional Religious system. Generally, the Yorùbá people hold that the human body and the spirit are separate units that make up the human essence. They are both separable but the absence of one will incapacitate the other. When the body is badly hurt, it is incapable of providing shelter for or sustaining the spirit further, the human ceases to exist. On the other hand, if, for one reason or the other, the spirit also departs the body, the body lies lifeless and is no better than a log of wood.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The difference between the spirit-mind and other body parts in the Yorùbá worldview is that while the spirit-mind outlasts other body parts as it is able to either re-incarnate or continue to exist after other body parts have ceased to live, other body parts return to dust and

perish after death.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Yoruba traditional religions view the spirit-mind as non-material, abstract, intangible and ontologically distinct from other body parts. They understand that though it cannot be physically held, touched or apprehended, it is nonetheless real.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Other aspects of the Yorùbá worldview about the human spirit and body indicates that though the spirit can depart its host (body) at death, it can repossess another individual and return either to the family where the deceased person who initially bore it in the previous life lived or to begin a new life elsewhere.. Thus the concepts of Àbíkú, ancestors returning as new born to their family and re-incarnation. In view of the continuous residence of ancestors with their families we see names as Babátúndé, Babájídé, Yétúndé and Yéjídé etc given to children born after the demise of their grandparents. The first two names speak of the fact that 'father has returned' while the latter speak of 'mother has returned'.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The Yorùbá speak of a life after this current one. Their idea of the next life however differs significantly from what the Abrahamic faiths practiced around them suggests.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Yorùbá speak of the after life as one to be lived in a perpetual cycle here on earth. The notions of heaven and hell are not popular among them. They hold that if an individual lived a commendable life in their previous sojourn on earth, such will get a better treatment in the next life still to be lived on the earth..

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Speaking of afterlife in a vaguely defined 'above' space, the Yorùbá make reference to a certain Ọrun Bàba Ẹni meaning 'the heaven of one's father'. They think of this heaven as a place above the skies where the good ancestors stay. It is described as a very pleasant place.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: Since the Yorùbá philosophy of the afterlife is one of re-incarnation, they think of the afterlife as a vaguely defined horizontal location where humans live, die and return to life on earth again in cycles..

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: This depends on whether in the previous life, the re-incarnated human lived a worthy life or a life full of wickedness. If the life lived previously was not lived well, such humans can return in a less dignifying form of life.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

Notes: This may sometimes be the case for those who lived in manners not measuring up to the standard set by the gods/deities in the Yorùbá worldview.

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

Notes: This is in line with the concept corporate rebirth as in the case of Babátúndé, Babájídé, Yétúndé and Yéjídé.

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: Cremation is not a popular treatment for corpses in the Yorùbá traditional religious system.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: Mummification is not a popular treatment for corpses in the Yorùbá traditional religious system.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The Yorùbá traditional religious system allowed co-sacrifices of humans, animals and other valuables in the past. This was usually done for the kings and nobles of the society so they could have a retinue of servants minister to their needs in the next life.

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: This was practiced in the past. It has been abolished among the Yorùbá people

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: Some traditions in Yorùbáland made a practice of this in the past.

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: Some traditions in Yorùbáland made a practice of this in the past.

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– Yes [specify]: Some traditions in Yorùbáland made a practice of this in the past. Other humans targeted for sacrifice in some parts of Yorùbáland in the past included albinos and people with hunch backs..

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Some traditions in Yorùbáland made a practice of this in the past.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Some traditions in Yorùbáland made a practice of this in the past. It is reported in some quarters that this is a voluntary practice of some families in Yorùbáland today where they bury certificates obtained by their aged parents with their corpses.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Some families made a practice of this in Yorùbáland in the past. It is still reported in some families or divisions of Yorùbáland today.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents of the various traditional religious groups among the Yorùbá believe in the existence of supernatural beings.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Although the Yorùbá traditional religious worldview supports in clear terms the existence of a supreme high God, they aver that he is now withdrawn from humans. He has therefore set deities in place to be intermediaries between him and humans. So all traditional religious movements in Yorùbáland have a deity they look up to. They are usually known as adherents of those deities. It is their belief that these deities represent the supreme being and that when they court their favour, pray to them and obey them, they will in turn present their matters to Olódúmarè who will receive their plea and answer their requests. Olódúmarè however has no cult, no devotees nor any representation. He is never directly approached by humans in the Yorùbá traditional religious system.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: In the Yorùbá traditional religious worldview, Olódúmarè is conceived as Olowogbogboro (one who has massive hands that are potent to save, rescue and protect those who seek refuge from him). He is seen as Eleni ateeke (one who has a large mat which he never folds up and on which he bears those who need his support perpetually)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Yorùbá traditional religious system acknowledges that the supreme high god resides beyond the skies. He is said to be withdrawn from human affairs and living in splendour.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is not fused with the monarch or king. However, kings are said to be igbákejì òrìsà (next in rank to the deities).

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Yorùbá traditional religious system sees monarchs as earthly representatives

of the divine being. However, other humans too are considered to be creations of the supreme being who are subjects to the authority of the kings as commanded by the deities and by extension, the supreme being himself.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: The supreme high god is the greatest of all that exists. He has given the deities charge over the earth while he keeps himself busy with other matters on the earth.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The Yorùbá traditional religious (YTR) adherents acknowledge the Olódúmarè (supreme being) as Arínú róde Olúmọ̀ràn ọ̀kàn. This means He is the all knowing. He sees the thoughts of the hearts and the intents of each action, deed and engagement.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Just as he knows the thoughts and intent of the heart/mind, the YTR adherents hold the supreme being as an all knowing God who knows the basic character or personal essence of every human being.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: He has all knowledge of this world including those that have never come to the understanding of mortal beings.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: YTR adherents acknowledge that the supreme being has deliberate causal efficacy in the world. They hold that his will is done on earth. This they affirm when they say *Ní àṣẹ̀ Olódúmarè* (may the sovereign will of the supreme being stand) or *Bí ò bá wu Olódúmarè* (if it pleases the supreme being)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: YTR adherents hold that the supreme being rewards all the deeds of every human being as they traverse the earth.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: YTR adherents hold that the supreme being punishes all the misdeeds of every human being as they traverse the earth.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: YTR adherents acknowledge that the supreme being has direct and not indirect causal efficacy in the world.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They see the supreme being as one who exhibits predominantly positive emotions in His interactions with human beings.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: YTR adherents hold that the supreme being exhibits His emotions mostly through his assistants whom humans refer to as deities. His positive and negative emotions are principally manifested through them. Sàngó, the god of thunder is held mostly as his instrument of fury and wrath hence the saying among the people, *Ẹní tí Sàngó bá t'ojú ẹ̀ jà kòní bú Ọba Kòso*. This means anyone who witnesses the fury of Sàngó will never join in insulting or crossing paths with the king of Kòso. Sàngó is widely held to have reigned over Kòso while he was still human. However, in line the traditions of the people, Sàngó has since become a deified ancestor around whom a thriving cult has been built.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: YTR adherents have cults built around several deities. They believe deities are the means to reaching the supreme being. So they worship the supreme being through the instrumentality of the deities.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The YTR adherents speak of communication with the supreme being in all their daily activities. They do this while on the way to the farm, in the markets, while in bed and in every other place.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The people speak of establishing communication with the supreme being in dreams.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The people speak of establishing communication with the supreme being in trance possession.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: As they visit the Ifá priests for consultations, they hear the supreme being speak to their situations and anxieties.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: YTR adherents speak of the supreme being communicating with them through religious specialists as through several other means as well.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through their circumstances, through the elements of nature and even through people considered as lunatics. They hold the latter as people not wholly human nor wholly spirits as they consider them as being able to attain certain realms of access into the spirit world.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Since they believe that the ancestors reside around/with them, they think of the fact that spirits of those who were previously human beings hover around them or reside within their immediate environment.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: YTR adherents do not speak of spirits of the departed ancestors and those of others who were previously humans around them as those which can be easily seen by mortal beings.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Spirits of those who were previously human around human populations cannot be easily felt except when they want themselves/their presence to be felt for specific reasons.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Their presence are usually restricted to the domain where they existed before their demise. Only the deified ancestors who have become objects of worship could begin to wield influence beyond the realms where they previously lived as human beings.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: This is mostly so except for the departed spirits of deified ancestors who have crossed the threshold of the usual spirits into the realm of active participants in the structure of the supernatural beings in the YTR framework.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: They are not given this privilege. It is only Olódúmarè and the gods who can see inside the hearts/minds.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: They may only have a partial knowledge of future events

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: They have the knowledge that they acquired about existence and the universe in the previous life.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: In the YTR worldview, human spirits do not possess the powers of deliberate causal efficacy in the world

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: In YTR worldview, human spirits have memory of life regarding only the things they became aware of during their times of life and living.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: This is not very common.

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

Notes: This is not common but its not to say that it never happens

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: In the Ifá corpus (the oral scriptures of the Yoruba Traditional religions) and other potent speeches among the Yoruba traditional religious groups, reference is made to the actions and interventions of Non-human supernatural beings and how their past deeds orchestrated in many ancient Yoruba settlements made a big difference in history. Such events serve as acid tests and reference as they give hope to devotees that as the deities performed heroic feats in the referenced ancient events, they will intervene in the matters for which they are being consulted.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: They have knowledge of events in the distant past which human beings scarcely know.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They could assist each other to achieve shared objectives
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba people hold that they can be seen in some cases. They are held as very dangerous to humans when they are encountered.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: They can be felt when they so wish.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Notes: They do not always know the basic character of human beings

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

– Yes [specify]: This includes knowledge acquired in the realm of the spirit.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: There are strange reports of how spirits like those who live in trees and in rivers prepare and eat food.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They are inherent or live in the skies and move with the air and winds. Some spirits possess humans, animals etc

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: Not always

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Not always

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Notes: Not always

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: These spirits possess human beings at times. They demand certain actions from those they possess. They communicate with them and ask them to carry out instructions which they have reeled out to them.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Classifications such as this is sometimes encountered. For example, Sàngó and Ọya were partners (husband and wife) before their demise. They were later deified as gods.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Olódúmarè sits as the head of all supernatural powers. He is followed by the primordial deities/gods. Next to these are the deified gods. We then have the spirits inhabiting all manner of strange places; spirits in trees, mountains, hills and rocks, rivers. After these are the ancestors.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the deities have certain food items they do not like to see or be presented with. Their adherents know the implications of doing otherwise than have been instructed by the gods. Èsù for example does not like Àdín, a local food item among the people.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are several sacred spaces in communities where the deities are worshipped. It is forbidden for some sets of people to venture into such sacred places. Some of them include forests, shrines, etc.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: There are a lot of sacred objects among worshippers of the YTR. They are not to be lightly esteemed or profaned. The divining tray is one of such sacred objects held by the diviner/Ifá priests.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is generally unacceptable to the supreme being, the deities and other supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is generally unacceptable to the supreme being, the deities and other supernatural beings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Most indigenous religious groups among the Yoruba dislike adultery as they see it as an evil which defiles the society.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Yoruba people naturally frown against incest. marriage is to be contracted by two adults who are not related by blood. In some traditional settings in Yorubaland, enquiries are made to ensure intending couples are not related at least from the last four generations.

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Homosexuality, lesbianism and bestiality are not accepted in a typical Yoruba village.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Although they hold the believe that the supernatural beings care about lying, there are instances the Yoruba think that a little lie will safe the day if a need for cover up arises.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
 - Notes: Sorcery is generally accepted in a typical Yoruba setting.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No
 - Notes: Supernatural beings do not really care about non-lethal fighting
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The cause or agent of supernatural punishment is sometimes known.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Sometimes, it is done by the high god and sometimes, it is done by other supernatural beings and circumstances.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: It may also be done by the universal law of Karma.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: It is sometimes known

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: It is sometimes done to maintain group discipline.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba talk about the after life (Èhinwá òla). They make reference to the fact that when people consider the afterlife and the punishments that await those who perpetrate evil, they are sometimes discouraged or dissuaded from doing evil or harming others.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: The people have a saying "Bí èniyàn bá n yó ilè dà ohun búburú a máa yówon se" meaning if anyone makes a habit of perpetrating evil in secret such fellow will also be experience evil in their closet. Such evil they experience in their closet is often regarded as bad luck until the cause of their misfortune is known to the public.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: This may happen in some instances.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: Causes/purposes of supernatural rewards are known in some instances

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
 - Notes: This is not necessarily so.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: Reward in this life could entail success in all of one's endeavours.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The groups which make up the YTR often have conventional norms. However, in some cases there appears to be a distinction between these conventions and the actual lives the adherents live.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Weakly present

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

Notes: In order to uphold good hygiene, the Yoruba have a belief which forbids people from sitting on mortar. This is a devise used for pounding grains, yams and other food items. They say that when an individual sits on the utensil, certain evils may befall them. wooden. The real issue they try to prevent here is the incidence abuse and contamination of the cooking devise.

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

Notes: The people forbid youngsters from collecting rain water falling off roof gutters. They claim that anyone who does so incurs the wrath of the gods and that when the thunder strikes, it will kill those who are found so doing. The idea behind this warning is to prevent young folks from contaminating water collected for domestic purposes and to keep them from getting wet from the sprays of the showers.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of

anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– Only specialized religious class

– Only one class of society

– Only one gender

– All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)

– All individuals within society

– All individuals within contemporary world

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: There are several categories of moral norms. Some of them apply to women, young folks, aliens/strangers while others apply to every member of the society.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: self control, passion for family bonding and cohesion etc

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Celibacy is not a common practice of indigenous religious groups in Yorùbáland

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: Although men are allowed to have multiple wives, they are not expected to be involved in romantic relationships with other married women.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Among the indigenous religious groups in Yorùbáland, married women are not expected to have other sexual partners apart from their husbands while unmarried ladies are to remain virgins until marriage.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: homosexual relationships and bestiality are not permitted in the traditional Yorùbá religious groups.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Incest is forbidden among the Yorùbá Traditional Religious groups.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not so pronounced among adherents of the Yorùbá Traditional Religious groups.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: There are taboos on certain food items by devotees of various religious groups indigenous to Yorùbáland

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is required in this religious group

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is required in this religious group

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is required in this religious group

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Members are required to attend religious gatherings and participate in rituals involving their religious group.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: marginalization by out-group members is not a requirement for members of the Traditional religious groups in No human sacrifice is required in this religious group. However, members of other faiths have come to see themselves as superior to them and therefore look down on them and cast aspersions upon them as they feel superior to adherents of the Yoruba Traditional Religions (YTR)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 24

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: Some of these religious groups hold large scale weekly rituals while others have a much longer time between their large scale rituals

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Orthodoxy checks are more visible between established religious specialists and their trainees who desire to assume the roles of religious specialists in their various groups. During rituals, worship or during times of need, (eg during spiritual warfare) certain incantations or potent words are expected to be recanted in the correct or prescribed manner in order to have the desired effects.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Orthopraxy checks are more visible between established religious specialists and their trainees who desire to assume the roles of religious specialists in their various groups. During rituals, worship or during times of need, (eg during spiritual warfare) certain incantations or potent words are expected to be recanted in the correct or prescribed manner in order to have the desired effects.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Intoxicants are widely used by some YTR groups in their worship and other ceremonies

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Extra ritual in-group markers are present in some of the traditional religious groups among the Yorùbá people. These in-group markers in some cases makes it easy to identify some of the religious specialists/functionaries in the midst of the crowd of worshippers/congregation.

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: It may be fitting to properly identify the array of body marks worn by some of the religious functionaries among the Yorùbá. Some of these body marks are not permanent as in the case of tattoos but are worn for ceremonial purposes. They include body paintings etc.

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Circumcision is an essential part of the Yorùbá culture. While males and females were generally circumcised in the past, female circumcision otherwise known as female genital mutilation has been discontinued in most parts of Yorùbáland and fast becoming a thing of the past in the remaining few places where it has not been fully abolished..

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the YTR groups have food taboos in place in their religious practices. The food taboos instituted by most of them include those food items which their deity forbids. These are foods they will never offer as sacrifices to the gods. The adherents will therefore be forbidden from eating such food items. If they intend to set an individual up against the deity/gods, they may present such foods as sacrifices to the gods and inform the deity that the item was presented to them by that individual. It is widely believed that the deity will fight such individual who is so named to have presented the food.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Hair styles also form part of in-group markers among the votaries of some YTR. For example, a certain group of male Sango worshippers usually braid their hair as a mark of devotion to their deity.

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Some dresses are unique to some classes of adherents among groups of worshippers in the YTR system. The Arugba Osun and priests of most YTR groups are classic examples of those whose dresses separate them from others during religious festivals/ceremonies.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the religious followers of deities among the YTR groups do adopt the use of ornaments in their worship and everyday life.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: This is not so common except for some use of archaic language in the rendition of oral

corpus/scriptures (Ese Ifa) of the YTR.

Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government sometimes makes promises of assisting members of the group with farm implements and supplies as many of the members of these groups are farmers.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Each family takes care of their elderly and infirm with their personal resources.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There are no strict bureaucracies within these groups.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with government establishments when the need arises.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Public food storages are not available to the people as a religious group. They are often made available to farmers generally while members of the groups may benefit not as people of a faith group but as farmers within a community comprising all manners of people.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Water management is often provided by the government through designated agencies of the state.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government and private business outfits provide transportation facilities to the populace.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The religious groups do not levy taxes or tithes. They seldom request money from members to take care of collective interests of the group.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government levies taxes on the citizens of which members of these groups are a part.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the Police administration set up under the control of the government.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the judicial system which is a part of the government of the land.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to the decisions of the judicial system set up by the government.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: This happens in criminal cases.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: This happens when the judgement handed a convicted criminal specifically states the inclusion of corporal punishments.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: This only happens when such property have been declared as proceeds of crimes or said to have been obtained fraudulently.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: There are the customary laws of Yorubaland in western Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Although these are religious groups indigenous to Yorubaland, the Yoruba language as it is today codified was reduced into writing in the second half of the seventeenth century much after the religion had been practiced for centuries.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Although the groups had their traditional way of counting weeks, months and years, the introduction of the Gregorian calendar has brought to them options for counting days, weeks and months.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Bolaji, Idowu. OLODUMARE: God in Yoruba Belief. London: Longmans, 1966.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Ologundudu, Dayo. The Cradle of Yoruba Culture. USA: Center for Spoken Words/ Institute of Yoruba Culture, 2008.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Rowlands, E. C.. "Book Review: Olodumare—god in Yoruba Belief" 65, no. 507 (September 1962). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0040571x6206550721>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Igboin, Benson O.. "Is Olodumare, God in Yoruba Belief, God?" 4, no. 2 (December 25, 2014). <https://doi.org/10.20871/kpjipm.v4i2.67>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Ogungbemi, Segun. "A Comparative Study of Olodumare, the Yoruba Supreme Being and the Judea-Christian God" 1, no. 1 (December 21, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.32473/ysr.v1i1.130014>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Abodunrin, Femi. "AFRICAN LITERATURE AND INDIGENOUS RELIGION: A STUDY OF WOLE SOYINKA'S DEATH AND THE KING'S HORSEMAN AND D.O. FAGUNWA'S ADIITU OLODUMARE" 7, no. 2 (May 26, 2017). <https://doi.org/10.25159/2078-9785/1854>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Layi, Oladipupo Sunday. "Is Olodumare, God in Yoruba Belief,

God?: A Response to Benson O. Igboin” 6, no. 1 (June 15, 2016). <https://doi.org/10.20871/kpjipm.v6i1.169>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Baëta, C. G.. “The Religion of the Yoruba - Olodumare, God in Yoruba Belief. By E. Bolaji Idowu. London: Longmans, 1962. Pp. 222. 27<i>s</i>. 6<i>d</i>.” 4, no. 1 (March 1963). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0021853700003807>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Hamonic, Gilbert. “God, Divinities and Ancestors. For the Positive Representation of a 'religious Plurality' in Bugis Society, South Sulawesi, Indonesia”. *Southeast Asian Studies* 29, no. 1 (June 1, 1991): 3-34.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Ogungbile, David O.. “Religion and the Making of Nigeria, Written by Olufemi Vaughan” 65, no. 2-3 (March 15, 2018). <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685276-12341501>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Gleason, Judith, Joseph M. Murphy, and Mei-Mei Sanford. “Osun Across the Waters: A Yoruba Goddess in Africa and the Americas” 45, no. 3 (December 2002). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1515144>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Gleason, Judith. “Oya in the Company of Saints”. *Journal of the American Academy of Religion* Vol.68, no. 2 (2000).

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Tidjani-Serpos, Nouréini. “The Postcolonial Condition: The Archeology of African Knowledge: From the Feat of Ogun and Sango to the Postcolonial Creativity of Obatala”. *Research in African Literatures* 27, no. 1 (1996): 2-18.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Gleason, Judith. “Oya in the Company of Saints”. *Journal of the American Academy of Religion* Vol.68, no. 2 (2000).

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Awolalu, Omosade. *Yoruba Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites*. Hallow, Essex, UK: Longman, 1981.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Arowolo, B. “Yoruba Deities in Aimé Césaire’s Dramaturgy” 3, no. 1 (August 28, 2008). <https://doi.org/10.4314/jpc.v3i1.36465>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Verger, Pierre. “Yoruba Influences in Brazil” 1, no. 2 (December 21, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.32473/ysr.v1i2.130174>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Apter, Andrew. “Notes on Orisha Cults in the Ekiti Yoruba Highlands. A Tribute to Pierre Verger” 35, no. 138 (1995). <https://doi.org/10.3406/cea.1995.1454>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Lloyd, P.C.. “Yoruba Myths: A Sociologist’s Interpretation” 1, no. 2 (December 21, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.32473/ysr.v1i2.130181>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Akintoye, Stephen Banji. “About the Name Yoruba” 5, no. 1 (December 21, 2021). <https://doi.org/10.32473/ysr.v5i1.130076>.

Reference: Yorùbá Traditional Religion, Falola, Toyin, and Jacob K. Olupona. “African Traditional Religions in Contemporary Society” 24, no. 2 (1991). <https://doi.org/10.2307/219809>.